

The Study of Cat Personalities Based on Coat Color: A Comparison between Theory and Survey Results

Chotiga Chotchaiphiboon¹

¹Yupparaj Wittayalai School 238 Phra Pok Klao Road, Sri Phum, Mueang, Chiang Mai 50200

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Abstract: Currently, there are many theories regarding the impact of cat coat color on personality traits. I aimed to compare the personalities of cats of different colors to see how closely they align with these theories. I collected data from a survey of 200 cat owners and found that the percentages of cats whose personalities matched the theories were as follows: orange cats 15.6%, white cats 25%, black cats 19.4%, calico cats 8.3%, tortoiseshell cats 15.8%, and tabby cats 34%. These findings suggest that a cat's coat color does not entirely determine its personality. It also depends on the rearing system, the care it receives, and traumatic events that may cause changes in its personality.

Keywords: cat, coat, personality, orange, white, black, calico, tortoiseshell, tabby.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, numerous theories exist linking cat coat color to specific personality traits, leading to common beliefs such as orange cats being friendly, calm, and easily trainable. This study aims to compare the actual personalities of cats of different coat colors with these theoretical expectations, using Homeowner's article "A Guide To Cat Personalities By Color Of Their Coats" by Logan Mastrianna as a reference point. Data from a Google Forms survey will be used to calculate the percentage of discrepancy and analyse the reasons why cat personalities might not align with the theorized traits associated with their coat color.

2. HYPOTHESIS

When comparing the personalities of cats based on coat color between the theory and the survey results, it was found that most cat personalities aligned with the theory. However, some discrepancies were observed. These variations can be attributed to factors such as upbringing, care, or past traumatic experiences that may have altered the cat's personalities. Therefore, some cats exhibit personality traits that do not conform to the expected traits associated with their coat color.

3. METHYDOLOGY

This is a non-experimental study with no controlled variables. I collected data from a Google Forms questionnaire, which constitutes primary data. This study included qualitative data collected from a total of 200 cat owners to analyze the results on the topic "The Study of Cat Personalities Based on Coat Color: A Comparison Between Theory and Survey Results." The questionnaire included the following questions: 1. Your gender 2. The coat color of your cat 3. The personality traits of your cat 4. The system you use to care for your cat 5. How often do you play with your cat each day? 6. Has your cat ever experienced a traumatic event that changed its personality? (If yes, please provide additional information) 7. What traumatic event caused your cat's personality to change?

The results were then compared with the following theories: 1. Orange cats are thought to have friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable personalities. 2. White cats are considered to have shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm personalities. 3. Black cats are believed to have highly independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals. 4. Calico cats are believed to have strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and are often vocal. 5. Tortoiseshell cats are thought to have stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners. 6. Tabby cats are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities.

4. RESULTS

This questionnaire collected data from a total of 200 cat owners, consisting of 145 females representing 72.5%, 25 males representing 12.5%, 22 LGBTQIA+ representing 11%, and 8 anonymous representing 4%. The breakdown of cat coat colors is as follows: 45 orange cats representing 22.5%, 28 white cats representing 14%, 31 black cats representing 15.5%, 24 tortoiseshell cats representing 12%, 19 calico cats representing 9.5%, and 53 tabby cats representing 26.5%.

TABLE 1: YOUR GENDER

Gender	Number of people	Percentage
Female	145	72.5
Male	25	12.5
LGBTQIA+	22	11
Anonymous	8	4

TABLE 2: THE COAT COLOR OF YOUR CAT

Coat color of cat	Number of cats	Percentage
Orange cats	45	22.5
White cats	28	14
Black cats	31	15.5
Calico cats	24	12
Tortoiseshell cats	19	9.5
Tabby cats	53	26.5

TABLE 3: THE PERSONALITIES OF ORANGE CATS

Personalities	Number of cats	Percentage
Friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable	7	15.6
Shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm	5	11.1
Independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals.	10	22.2
Strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and often vocal	4	8.9
Stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners.	5	11.1
Courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn	14	31.1

The survey results show that the majority of orange cats, totaling 14, are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities, representing 31.1%. According to the theory, the personality

traits of orange cats are supposed to be friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable. In the survey, 7 cats matched this theory, representing 15.6%.

TABLE 4: THE PERSONALITIES OF WHITE CATS

Personalities	Number of cats	Percentage
Friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable	3	10.7
Shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm	7	25
Independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals.	7	25
Strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and often vocal	1	3.6
Stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners.	3	10.7
Courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn	7	25

The survey results show that the majority of white cats, totaling 7, are considered to have shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm personalities, representing 25%. Additionally, 7 cats are believed to have highly independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals, representing 25%. Furthermore, 7 cats are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities, representing 25%. According to the theory, the personality traits of white cats are supposed to be shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm. In the survey, 7 cats matched this theory, representing 25%.

TABLE 5: THE PERSONALITIES OF BLACK CATS

Personalities	Number of cats	Percentage
Friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable	5	16.1
Shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm	6	19.4
Independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals.	6	19.4
Strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and often vocal	3	9.7
Stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners.	4	12.9
Courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn	7	22.6

The survey results show that the majority of black cats, totaling 7, are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities, representing 22.6%. According to the theory, the personality traits of black cats are supposed to be independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals. In the survey, 6 cats matched this theory, representing 19.4%.

TABLE 6: THE PERSONALITIES OF CALICO CATS

Personalities	Number of cats	Percentage
Friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable	4	16.7
Shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm	2	8.3
Independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals.	4	16.7
Strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and often vocal	2	8.3
Stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners.	6	25
Courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn	6	25

The survey results show that the majority of calico cats, totaling 6, are considered to have stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners, representing 25%. Additionally, 6 cats are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities, representing 25%. According to the theory, the personality traits of calico cats are supposed to be strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and are often vocal. In the survey, 2 cats matched this theory, representing 8.3%.

TABLE 7: THE PERSONALITIES OF TORTOISESHELL CATS

Personalities	Number of cats	Percentage
Friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable	4	21.1
Shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm	0	0
Independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals.	6	31.6
Strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and often vocal	0	0
Stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners.	3	15.8
Courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn	6	31.6

The survey results show that the majority of tortoiseshell cats, totaling 6, are believed to have highly independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals, representing 31.6%. Additionally, 6 cats are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities, representing 31.6%. According to the theory, the personality traits of tortoiseshell cats are supposed to be stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners, 3 cats matched this theory, representing 15.8%.

TABLE 8: THE PERSONALITIES OF TABBY CATS

Personalities	Number of cats	Percentage
Friendly, affectionate, calm, and trainable	7	13.2
Shy, loyal, affectionate, kind, and calm	5	9.4
Independent, unpredictable, and tolerant personalities towards people and other animals.	10	18.9
Strong, lively, energetic, loving personalities towards their owners and often vocal	8	15.1
Stubborn, brave, confident, kind personalities and enjoy playing with their owners.	5	9.4
Courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn	18	34

The survey results show that the majority of tabby cats, totaling 18, are thought to have courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn personalities, representing 34%. According to the theory, the personality traits of tabby cats are supposed to be courageous, playful, friendly, active, exploratory, and occasionally stubborn. In the survey, 18 cats matched this theory, representing 34%.

TABLE 9: THE SYSTEM YOU USE TO CARE FOR YOUR CAT

The system	Number of cats	Percentage
outdoor	112	56
indoor	88	44

The survey results show that there are 112 cats kept indoors, representing 56%, and 88 cats kept outdoors, representing 44%.

TABLE 10: HOW OFTEN DO YOU PLAY WITH YOUR CAT EACH DAY?

Hours	Number of people	Percentage
Less than 1 hour	51	25.5
1-3 hours	103	51.5
4-6 hours	28	14
More than 6 hours	18	9

The survey results show that there are 51 owners who play with their cats for less than 1 hour per day, representing 25.5%. There are 103 owners who play for 1-3 hours per day, representing 51.5%. There are 28 owners who play for 4-6 hours per day, representing 14%, and 18 owners who play for more than 6 hours per day, representing 9%.

TABLE 11: HAS YOUR CAT EVER EXPERIENCED A TRAUMATIC EVENT THAT CHANGED ITS PERSONALITIES?

Choice	Number of cats	Percentage
Never	173	86.5
Ever	27	13.5

The survey results show that there are 173 cats that have never experienced a traumatic event that changed its personality, representing 86.5%. There are 27 cats that have ever experienced a traumatic event that changed its personality, representing 13.5%.

TABLE 12: WHAT TRAUMATIC EVENT CAUSED YOUR CAT'S PERSONALITY TO CHANGE?

Traumatic event	Number of cats	Percentage
Attacked by a dog	4	14.8
Attacked by a cat	4	14.8
Attacked by a person	2	7.4
Put in a laundry basket and became scared	1	3.7
Leg stuck in a chair	1	3.7
Spayed/neutered	2	7.4
Lost their owner	1	3.7
Moved house	1	3.7
Chased away and acted like stomping feet	2	7.4
Afraid of car sounds	1	3.7
Left alone at home	1	3.7
Taken for a bath and got hit	1	3.7
Lost a family member	3	11.1
Afraid of people	3	11.1

The survey results show that the majority of cats, totaling 4, have been attacked by dogs, representing 14.8%. Additionally, 4 cats have been attacked by other cats, also representing 14.8%.

5. DISCUSSION

Based on a study of 200 cats, it was found that 15.6% of orange cats exhibited personality traits consistent with the theory, while 25% of white cats did, 19.4% of black cats, 8.3% of calico cats, 15.8% of tortoiseshell cats, and 34% of tabby cats. The reason most cats have personality traits that do not align with their coat color according to the theory is due to the system you use to care for your cat. In outdoor environments, cats are more likely to develop stubborn, playful, unpredictable, and aggressive traits compared to indoor cats. Additionally, the number of hours owners spend playing with their cats each day affects their behavior. Cats whose owners play with them more tend to be friendlier, more obedient, and better bonded with their owners than those that receive less playtime. Furthermore, cats that have experienced traumatic events are more likely to exhibit fearful, paranoid, shy, and skittish behaviors compared to those that have not faced such events.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on a study of 200 cats using a questionnaire, it was found that 15.6% of orange cats exhibited personality traits consistent with the theory, 25% of white cats, 19.4% of black cats, 8.3% of calico cats, 15.8% of tortoiseshell cats, and 34% of tabby cats. Therefore, a cat's coat color cannot fully indicate its personality, as it also depends on the rearing system, the care it receives, and traumatic events that may cause changes in its personality.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lookman, Saleema. (2023, April 21). See What Your Cat's Color Says About Their Personality. Love to know pets. <https://www.lovetoknowpets.com/cats/see-what-your-cats-color-says-about-their-personality>
- [2] Mastrianna, Logan. (2024, September 27). A Guide To Cat Personalities By Color Of Their Coats. Homeowner. <https://www.homeowner.com/cats/cat-personalities-by-color>
- [3] Wu, Karen. (2020, November 29). 8 Factors That Contribute to a Cat's Personality. Psychology Today. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/gb/blog/the-modern-heart/202011/8-factors-contribute-cat-s-personality>